

DEVELOPING CRITICAL CAREER THEORY

Exploring the conceptual underpinning
of the *Critical approaches to career
and career guidance* project

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ABSTRACT

This position paper argues for the development of a coherent body of critical career theory that responds to contemporary crises of inequality, precarity, and ecological breakdown. It rejects individualising models and synthesises diverse traditions into practice principles that cultivate critical consciousness and connect guidance to collective, organisational and policy change. Situated amid precarity, platformisation, automation, ecological transition and widening inequality, the argument defends bounded yet real agency. It also outlines our **COST Action** agenda to map theory, strengthen the evidence base and shift institutions. The outcome is a clearer field with a shared vocabulary and a practical plan for research, pedagogy and policy.

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INTRODUCTION

We live in a world of extremes in which societies face new challenges. The world order that was based on Bretton Woods and other international institutions developed at the end of the Second World War is increasingly called into doubt. We have moved from a system of global superpowers (US and USSR), to one of U.S. hegemony, and now to a complex world of multipolarity in which many of the geopolitical heuristics of the past can no longer be relied on. Meanwhile, Covid-19, ongoing armed conflicts across the globe, tariff wars and increasing turbulence in global value chains have brought economic devastation, labour market instability, and reduced access to decent work. Capitalism has evolved in ways that have resulted in wage stagnation, increased inequality and growing precarity. And all these changes are taking place against the ticking clock of the climate crisis and an existential angst about the place of humanity in a world of increasing automation and artificial intelligence which threatens to displace some workers and transform the nature of work. (Baruch & Vardi, 2016).

Not since the Second World War has there been a period in the EU or OECD countries when young people entering the labour market could expect a life with lower pay than their parents. The acronyms PINE (poorly integrated new entries) and NEET (not in Education, Employment or Training) have become key terms describing the challenge of transition into the labour market that younger generations face. In many countries, social mobility is slowing down or even going into reverse. Increasingly it is difficult for people to believe that their children will have a better life than they have had, thus the modern premise of 'progress', with its promise of a 'secular salvation' comes into question (Gee, 2019).

The labour market itself is also in a process of transformation with access to remote and blended working expanding, alongside the growth of precarious work. The technological revolution threatens to replace many jobs. Even those employed within the large public or private corporations that have historically provided stable career ladders have seen an erosion of the psychological contract and the decline of trade unions and collective bargaining.

Bauman (2000) called this late (post)-modernity a liquid modernity. Liquid modernity in which individualisation acts as the main form of socialisation defragments communities and social bonds and consequently has had important implications for career theory and the policy and practice of career guidance (Lucas Casanova et al., 2019). Beck (1992) described contemporary societies as 'risk society' in which capitalism is increasing the risks experienced by both individuals and societies. Cascio (2000) describes this as BANI society, in which careers are Brittle, Anxious, Nonlinear and Incomprehensible. However, these accounts of contemporary capitalism were written before the current period of crisis and the period that we have been living since the financial crisis of 2007/2008 has been accompanied by entreaties for workers to remain relevant and resilient amidst these volatile conditions.

Career adaptability was viewed as one of the greatest virtues for individuals in such situations and has formed the basis for much career theory during the neoliberal period with little attention on its political implications (Johnston, 2018; Gee, 2022a). In the current period of crisis, it is no longer clear whether contemporary society can fully be captured by the metaphors of liquidity or risk, but it is clear that career adaptability is insufficient as a strategy to guarantee people access to the good life or stand in for a failing welfare system. Consequently, we are in the midst of an ongoing, dynamic transformation, which in turn necessitates the creation of new forms of career theory.

The level of capitalist crisis described above has reduced many people's chances of building a positive and meaningful career/ life that allows them to access the good life. This has been exacerbated by the fact that in the face of global turbulence, many countries have chosen to reduce social welfare and increase disciplinary forms of conditionality for those wishing to access the welfare state. These various trends amount to a dismantling of the career ladders that previously existed to allow some people to develop their careers and progress in their life, learning and work, though the myth of such 'progress' lingers within individual desire and social discourses of meritocracy.

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Geopolitical and economic shifts mean that the explanatory power of traditional career theory has waned. The development of much career theory happened during a period of relative capitalist stability and was largely focused on the experience of the working and middle classes in the Euro-Atlantic countries. Not only has the context changed, but there is a growing critique which demands that career theory is expanded to encompass the experience of a more diverse range of people including the poor, women, those in the Global South, people with disabilities and racially minoritised groups (Buford, & Flores, 2025; Richardson, 2012; Ribeiro, 2021).

The question as to whether there is an alternative to the current way of living and governing society is therefore a critical one. The consensus has been that there is no alternative and that the best that we can hope for is either better technocratic management of the current system, or the weighting of the scales in favour of our country, ethnic group or community in a way that affords (unfair) advantage to some of us. The idea that 'there is no alternative' or TINA harks back to an earlier period of neoliberalism in which capitalism reigned supreme, and the Soviet model was increasingly discredited (Berlinski, 2011). Fisher (2009) notes that it has become easier to imagine the end of the world, whether through climate crisis or nuclear war, than it is to imagine the end of capitalism.

TINA has created a remarkable failure of the political imagination in which almost all possibilities have been taken off the table of mainstream politics. Yet since 2008, capitalism has suffered repeated crises and challenges, whilst largely continuing to maintain a consensus in the mainstream media and politics around TINA. There has been a creeping normalisation of 'zero-sum' populist politics based on ideas that if one group wins, another loses rather than seeking ways to create a world where everyone can thrive.

Meanwhile there has been a swelling in the ranks of billionaires. In 2025 Forbes estimated that there were 3,028 billionaires in the world and that they are collectively worth \$16.1 trillion in all, which is more than the GDP of every country in the world besides the U.S. and China (Peterson-Withorn, 2025). We live in an age of plenty, and yet people are starving, welfare states are threadbare, and politicians constantly tell us that we must tighten our belts.

Such a world feels dystopian, especially as vast inequalities that were once only experienced by colonial subjects move into the developed world (Gee et al., 2025). Optimism and hope are increasingly hard to come by. In previous eras we might have looked to technology as an engine of progress and a tool for delivering better lives. But the promise of automation and artificial intelligence has now become yet another source of dystopian angst. Virilio (2012) describes such changes as 'derailment' in which what appeared to be a technology that could better human existence is revealed to have an unanticipated dark side. Gee (2022a) argues that the very idea of progress can be seen as a form of propaganda seeking to buy us all into an inhumane cult of speed. Such concerns are leading policymakers, commentators, workers and citizens to ask whether the robots will rise to take away workers' jobs, delivering the ultimate capitalist fantasy of production without labour (Ford, 2015)? Or will AI achieve consciousness, or at least a passable simulacrum of it, and conclude that humanity is an unnecessary inconvenience which might be helpfully tidied into its grave? Meanwhile the democratic promise of the internet has given way to surveillance and platform capitalism in which our private lives are commodified, manipulated and extracted, all in service of the production of more billionaires (Srnicek, 2017; Zuboff, 2019).

This story is a dark and dystopian one. Those with a more optimistic bent might point to a host of counter trends. Of centuries-old traditions of struggle and resistance, of enduring welfare state systems and guarantees of human rights, of functioning, if imperfect, democracies, of political movements fighting for a better world, of improvements to public health and of changing social attitudes and of enhanced living standards for ordinary people across the world, which go on despite these dark trends and include the provision of help, support, solidarity and mutual aid to friends, family, colleagues and even strangers. The world may be dystopian, but it is not yet a dystopia, there is still room for hope and optimism, for the belief that a better world is possible, that we are not at the end of history and that consequently there are alternatives which can be both dreamt and realised.

Critical social science is a multifaceted approach to social inquiry that goes beyond mere description and analysis, seeking to understand and challenge power structures, inequalities, and social injustices.

Yet, such a world of extremes poses important questions for those of us who research, study, teach and practice in the interdisciplinary field of career studies. Is career really the most important thing to study in such times? Would we not be better turning our attention to questions of economic organisation, social attitudes or political movements? And if we are going to study career, how can we consider the problematic nature of the concept and the way in which much career guidance is understood as a technology for ushering people uncritically into participation in the capitalist market (Collin, 2011; Hooley et al., 2018a; Sultana, 2014a). This paper will seek to set out a response to this and explain why critical theory is central to this response. Critical social science is a multifaceted approach to social inquiry that goes beyond mere description and analysis, seeking to understand and challenge power structures, inequalities, and social injustices. It aims to not only describe the world but also to inspire change and emancipation (Thomsen et al., 2022a). We will also introduce the *Critical approaches to career and career guidance (COAG)* project and explain how this project hopes to take these questions and actions forward.

WHY CAREERS MATTER

In its vernacular or 'everyday' form the concept of career is often understood as relating primarily, or even solely, to an individual's experience of paid work. Sometimes it is considered even more narrowly as relating to professional forms of paid work, which offer individuals opportunities to climb up occupational or organisational hierarchies. Thomsen and Hooley (2025) note that:

When, in conversation, we tell people that we are professors and 'careers' is our field of study, a common response is: Oh, I don't have a career. I've just had a succession of jobs. Such reactions are based on the idea that a 'career' is associated with success, orderly progression up an organisational hierarchy, and social status – that a career is a ladder, and there is only one way to climb it.

(pp.28-29)

Yet, such definitions are only one way to describe the concept of career. Ernesto Laclau (1996/2007) noted that there are a range of concepts in society, whose meaning is regularly contested by different kinds of actors to make a point and advance their agenda. He calls such concepts *empty signifiers* and argues that with such terms, the important question is not 'what does this really mean' which assumes that one definition is right, and all the others are technically flawed. This also relates to the notion of a 'floating signifier' originated by linguists such as Lévi-Strauss (1951) and utilised in theories exploring 'race' (Hall, 2006), and 'youth' (Côté, 2014). A floating signifier is a sign whose meaning is unstable, and which moves between possible meanings. The important point here is that we should be looking at the way in which the meaning of empty and floating signifiers is contested. Such definitional battles serve as a terrain on which struggles are fought, as exemplified by Bergmo-Prvulovic (2018).

Providing a definition for a term like 'career' is not a technical act, but rather a political one in which we seek to intervene into an ideological field and shape it. Hence, a definition also signals an ambition or an intention for the concept or word, it says something about what we want it to be (Koselleck & White, 2002; Koselleck, 2004). This is an important consideration for 'career', as Collin and Young point out, 'career' (potentially incorporating aspects of employment) can become a tempting space (and place) to 'organise reflexive activities' due to its ability to comprise and simultaneously express competing meanings without 'falling apart' or 'becoming meaningless' (Collin & Young, 2000, p.173).

We argue that the concept of career is exactly this kind of culturally situated/ideological concept with different definitions which variously conceptualise it as a race or a journey, or as an individual, organisational or societal good and property (Inkson, 2004; Law, 2008; Watts, 1996a). Such different definitions are not merely engaging in some academic quibble, but rather in an important political struggle about the nature of life and work and the possibility of individual and collective agency within it. So, when McCash et al. (2021) argue that:

Career is not a single moment of decision when we choose one job over another. It is deeply woven into the ongoing fabric of our lives. Our careers are conducted continuously, and they develop in social and political contexts that provide contrasting opportunities and limitations. Career is all around us and there is no escape from it, because it describes the coming together of our life, our learning, and our work. Career is important to the lives of individuals across the world and to the societies in which they live."

(pp.8-9)

They are making a political statement in which the concept of career is being situated as politically contextual, broader than paid work and simultaneously a public and a private good. Such ideological and definitional work is not about finding the correct definition of the concept of career, but rather about imagining a concept of career which is conducive to the good life for the majority of people.

Such a definition of career attends to the importance of paid work but is not defined exclusively by it. This kind of definition has become highly influential within the academic field of career studies. It goes beyond the vernacular concept of work-life balance and instead positions careering as a way in which individuals negotiate the time, effort and attention that they give to the various parts of their life including hobbies and creative endeavours, family life, learning and citizenship as well as paid and unpaid, formal and informal forms of work (see Blustein, 2011).

By viewing career from a lifelong perspective (Bergmo-Prvulovic, 2024), we are able to grasp how the concept of career is a bridging object, and as such serves to link institutional contexts with each other. Bergmo-Prvulovic (2024) encourages us to pay attention to the individuals' contextual movements and transitions from one context to another, from one stage to another, from one phase to another including their internal movements of personal growth and learning throughout their career navigation. It is here, within the gaps, within the liminal spaces of being in between, the potential of new approaches to career and career guidance are embedded.

One concern is that such a broadening of the definition of career runs the risk of thinking the concept out of business. Is such a broad definition of life tasks and activities not better thought of just as 'life'? But we could argue that 'career' captures more fully the trade-offs and inter-relationships that exist between these different strands of life on both a day-to-day level and across the life course. The terminology of 'strands' is borrowed from Goffman (1961) and used to define any activity or development that links a life narrative together (Gee, 2017) – To career is not merely to be alive, but rather to seek some agency and control over your life, whilst navigating the opportunity structure and looking forward to a future horizon (Roberts, 2009; Hodkinson, 2009). As Krumboltz and Levin (2004) noted, such careering cannot be fully rational, particularly if measured in economic terms, nor fully planned. Rather careering is a process of managing uncertainty and the chaotic interaction of the individual and the world around them.

Such thinking positions the concept of career as a philosophical, political and sociological lens or tool of analysis which can help to mediate between structure, culture and agency debates whilst accounting for uncertainty (Archer, 2007). We make our careers, but not in the circumstances of our own choosing. Careers happen in a recursive relationship between our psychology and social institutions and structures. We do not just work, but rather work for an employer, or for ourselves, with these different structural arrangements affecting, not only our work-selves but also, our family lives, leisure time and capacity to engage with the political world. Similarly, our engagement in these other spheres, is not helpfully understood as separate from our work, but rather as both intertwined and in tension with it.

Work transforms the world, and we are transformed through our relationship with the world and others through work, allowing both the affirmation of our singularity (an individual who can transform the world) and our position within the multitude of other actors. Marx, like many other philosophers argues that this allows us to view all human activity as a form of work and humanity as defined by its capacity for work and transformation (*homo faber*) (Marx, 1867/1887; 1939/1973). Such a position is not a negation of leisure, but rather a recognition that what is referred to as leisure can also be a process of transformation of the world and therefore viewed as a form of work, even if it comes about without the discipline of wage labour and associated economic pressure. Of course, leisure does not exist as a pure category outside of capitalism but rather interacts with it in ways that both challenge and legitimise the economic ideology which places paid work at the top of the pyramid of human endeavours (Clarke & Critcher, 1985; Rojek, 1999). The temporal nature of careers is also central here, as it highlights the fact that we are not simply existing in the moment, trying for example, to achieve maximum return for our effort or a good work-life balance this week, but rather playing off the now against the imagined and desired future.

Hopefully this discussion about career has begun to demonstrate that in the introduction to this paper we established a false opposition between the dramatic world of big politics and the private process of careering or what Wright Mills (1959) refers to as the distinction between public issues and private troubles. Instead, we would argue that thinking about careers is highly relevant to thinking about the kind of crisis political economy in which we currently live. Career provides us with a lens to consider how we and others can live in an imperfect world, as well as providing us with tools to think about how such a world can be changed and transformed by the work we do, the relationships we build and the lives that we live.

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CAREER GUIDANCE FOR SOCIAL JUSTICE

The contemporary concept of career emerged during the industrial revolution to provide a mechanism for individuals to participate in a new type of society. The concept of career is therefore value-laden insofar as it bears the imprint of the social division of labour and the political system. Careers were framed by 'master and servant acts' in the 18th and 19th centuries which sought to begin the regulation of industrial relations, the emergence of the trade union movement, and finally the development of the first global standards for decent work with the birth of the International Labour Organization (ILO). It is not self-evident that decent jobs, non-exploitative working hours, and labour regulations are available in a country.

For example, the institutional weekend did not emerge until the 19th century as a result of a variety of religious, cultural and industrial pressures including the campaigning of the trade union movement and the gradual willingness of government to regulate the labour market. Yet, such a progression towards decent work is not inevitable and in the periods of neoliberal hegemony and crisis capitalism many of the gains that workers experienced throughout the 19th and 20th century have once more been open to renegotiation.

In the 21st century, labour markets have required increasing flexibility from workers, leading in many cases to growing precarity and worsening employment conditions. Some have argued that there is a need to reconceptualise the labour market, and therefore careers, in ways that provide better work-lives for people (Borbély-Pecze, 2020). One such approach is described as the Transitional Labour Markets (TLMs) which refers to a policy-oriented view of labour markets that focuses on managing the transitions individuals make between different employment statuses and activities throughout their lives. It recognises that individuals move between employment, unemployment, and inactivity, and that these transitions can be supported by institutional arrangements. TLMs aim to ensure social security and individual agency during these transitions by providing support during critical life stages like the shift from education to work, or from homemaking to employment (Schmid, 2017).

The argument so far has been to recognise career as a lens through which the relationship between individuals, communities, social institutions and societies can be understood. But such an observation raises a further question, which is, if career is intertwined with the political economy, is it possible to relate to people and their careers in ways that allow them to navigate the opportunity structures within which they are living, build meaningful lives and potentially shape and transform the social structures?

Purposeful interventions in careers have a long history which stretch back beyond the start of the twentieth century (Savickas, 2008; Williamson, 1964). While such interventions can be given a variety of names, we can generically describe them as 'career guidance'. Hooley et al. (2018b) summarise this as follows:

Career guidance supports individuals and groups to discover more about work, leisure and learning and to consider their place in the world and plan for their futures... Career guidance can take a wide range of forms and draws on diverse theoretical traditions. But at its heart it is a purposeful learning opportunity which supports individuals and groups to consider and reconsider work, leisure and learning in the light of new information and experiences and to take both individual and collective action as a result of this."

(p.20)

Yet, this definition is not simply a technical description of the activity of career guidance. Rather it was created as a definitional intervention into the empty signifier of 'career guidance'. In essence it echoes the OECD's (2004) definition of career guidance but introduces new concepts like 'leisure' and 'collective action' to emphasise 'career guidance as a dialogic, mutually pedagogic relationship, which can support conscientization and the development of political skills and community resources and inspire people to transform the social realities, within which they find themselves' (p.20).

Such definitional battles highlight that career guidance is inherently political. As Watts (1996b, p.225) puts it.

Careers education and guidance is a profoundly political process. It operates at the interface between the individual and society, between self and opportunity, between aspiration and realism. It facilitates the allocation of life chances. Within a society in which such life chances are unequally distributed, it faces the issue of whether it serves to reinforce such inequalities or to reduce them."

Depending on who has access to it, how it is deployed and what it seeks to achieve, it can be used for a wide range of different purposes. Sultana (2014b) argues that there are three main rationalities that underpin career guidance. Firstly, technocratic rationalities that emphasise career guidance as a technology of efficiency, designed to bring education and employment into greater alignment and shape individuals aspirations and subjectivities in the interest of the economy and the labour market. Examples might include government using career guidance to steer people into STEM subjects, towards vocational education and apprenticeships or into sectors which are experiencing particular skills shortages.

Sultana's second rationality is developmental and emphasises the way in which career guidance can support the life project of individuals. Such approaches focus on concepts like self-efficacy and self-actualisation to help people to find the best way of living within the current structures typically through a process of adaption and the development of resilience. Examples of developmental rationalities might encompass both the person-centred counselling of Rogers (1995/1961) and the life-design paradigm (Savickas et al., 2009) which has dominated much thinking about career guidance in recent years.

Finally, Sultana highlights the emancipatory rationality, which views the development of the individual (and indeed the group, community or collective) alongside the development of society and social structures. Such approaches 'give pride of place to raising consciousness, to uncovering structures and patterns of injustice, to providing citizens with the tools to resist, contest, and transform, and to working on the behalf of clients through all sorts of advocacy' (Sultana, 2014b, p.19).

Whereas, technocratic and developmental approaches encourage 'realism' and the acceptance of structural constraints, emancipatory approaches seek to stimulate the sociological imagination and expand the possible. Emancipatory approaches, in the words of Mark Fisher (2009, p.17), 'must always destroy the appearance of a 'natural order', must reveal what is presented as necessary and inevitable to be a mere contingency, just as it must make what was previously deemed to be impossible seem attainable'. And it is in this emancipatory rationality and in the practice of emancipatory forms of career guidance that this paper and the current project are primarily interested.

Sultana was far from the first person to observe the emancipatory potential of career guidance. Some would argue that a commitment to social justice goes back to the origins of the field (O'Brien, 2001). Willis' seminal ethnography *Learning to labour* (1978/2017) contains detailed reflections on forms of emancipatory guidance. Work by Bates (1990) sought to bring the study of labour relations and social and economic power differences into careers education and guidance, whilst Richardson (2012) challenged normative ideas about what constitutes work and career and argued for career guidance to frame its purpose much more broadly and inclusively. But it was perhaps in Irving and Malik's (2004) volume *Critical reflections on career education and guidance* that emancipatory, or as we style them here critical, approaches really began to emerge as a distinct strand of career guidance theory and practice.

Subsequently there has been an explosion of work which has looked at career guidance and social justice. This includes further work by Ronald Sultana, often with his colleagues Tristram Hooley and Rie Thomsen (Hooley & Sultana, 2016; Hooley et al., 2018; 2019a), and work by David Blustein and his colleagues in the US, who built on the theories around the psychology of working theory (Blustein, 2013; Diemer et al., 2016). Empirically, one way to venture into the realm of social justice in careers has been to look at the relationship between context and careers. Literature coming out of this perspective has shown that the universal, hegemonic and inherently western way of understanding careers as organisational ladders to climb, leaves career guidance in danger of not being relevant to a lot of people, either because such careers do not exist in their life-space (Alexander, 2018) or because work-cultures simply do not see ladder-climbing as the best way to have a fulfilling worklife (Bakke, 2020, 2024). In other words, it is an important aspect of social justice in careers that career guidance needs to be made relevant to *most people* to be in a position to work towards emancipation. Importantly this has also included a growing range of work representing epistemologies from the Global South, indigenous communities and others who have been made vulnerable by neoliberalism (Ribeiro, 2021).

It is also important to note that such social justice informed career guidance practices do not simply exist in the academic literature but can also be found in practice. To clarify what such practices look like it is useful to briefly outline a few examples.

Chronister and McWhirter (2006) describe a powerful career guidance intervention that was developed for women who had experienced domestic violence. The intervention included discussions with the women about their values, journaling, skills assessments, an introduction to sources of community support, role modelling, clarification of goals, group work, critical self-reflection and reflection on power and domestic violence experiences. This content was organised through a five-week curriculum and was designed to increase the confidence of the women, their capacity to move their career forward and their critical consciousness, particularly in relation to the dynamics of domestic violence. Such an intervention can be viewed as an example of emancipatory career guidance for several reasons, including its focus on an oppressed group and its willingness to actively address this oppression in relation to career, but also because of its holistic nature and the recognition that life-experience, relationships, psycho-social wellbeing and work and employment cannot be separated out. Finally, the focus on critical consciousness as an outcome of the intervention links it to a long-standing tradition of critical education stretching back to Freire (1970/2005) and beyond.

A different example can be seen in Cox's (2022) description of a careers workshop delivered as part of a second-year undergraduate module within a Comparative Literature degree. The workshop encouraged students to use the research and analytical skills that they had developed in their literature degree to analyse the gendered coding found in job advertisements (Gaucher et al., 2011). This process subjected a typically unnoticed social norm to scrutiny helping students to see that labour market segregation is neither natural, nor a simple expression of their preferences, but is rather something that is

actively produced. Therefore, the intervention can be understood as a form of socially just career guidance because it challenges the appearance of the natural order and builds participants' critical consciousness. Career is overtly presented as being an interaction between the individual and social institutions in an unequal society and participants in the guidance are invited to critique this and develop a range of responses to it.

Similarly, Gee and colleagues have introduced forms of career education that explore undergraduate students' understandings of social structures, social position and how this might influence career trajectory and how can they navigate this collectively to challenge such structures and navigate in solidarity (Gee, 2022b; Gee et al., 2025a). Other authors (Cunningham et al, 2024) have utilised the concept of decent or good work in career learning pedagogy as a way to stimulate new imaginaries about what work could or should be. The expanding literature about green guidance (Bakke et al, 2024) represents a clear shift in encouraging practitioners to address the global challenge of climate change in practical interventions with clients.

The recognition that there are a range of examples of emancipatory career guidance led Hooley et al. (2019b) to develop the five signposts model as a way of theorising emancipatory career guidance. This model was originally developed to summarise the range of perspectives presented in *Career guidance for social justice* and *Career guidance for emancipation* (Hooley et al., 2018; 2019a) in a way that could be translated into practice (Hooley et al., 2019b). It has subsequently been developed further in publications to serve as a useful intermediary tool between theory and practice (Hooley et al., 2021; Schulstok et al., 2024; Thomsen et al., 2022b).

The signposts offer five features that can be seen as comprising emancipatory forms of career guidance practice. They note that a critical or emancipatory approach to careers guidance would do the following things.

- **Build critical consciousness** by helping people to achieve a deep, contextual understanding of the life situation that they are in and consider a wide range of ways that they can act on the world to improve their situation.
- **Name oppression** by helping people see injustice and organise in solidarity to access a decent career.
- **Question what is normal** by spending time discussing what normality means and whether it is necessarily desirable.
- **Encourage people to work together** by facilitating social interaction and collaboration and helping people to recognise that giving and receiving mutual aid is critical to career development.
- **Work at a range of levels.** Career practitioners need to be willing to work at a range of levels from the individual to the global and support their students to do the same.

Underpinning these five signposts is the imperative of advocacy, the proactive engagement with structural power to enable equitable access to meaningful and sustainable careers. Advocacy emerges as a central component of emancipatory approaches. It involves career professionals working not only with individuals, but also on their behalf to identify systemic barriers and actively engaging with institutions, employers, policymakers and communities to promote more equitable access to opportunities (Midttun & McCash, 2018). Advocacy complements consciousness-raising by extending the influence of career guidance beyond the counselling room into the social and political arenas where life chances are shaped. Advocacy includes naming and resisting injustice, building alliances, and pushing for systemic reform. This is especially critical for marginalised groups who face layered and enduring barriers to decent work, social mobility and voice. Effective career guidance must take account of how different groups are disproportionately impacted by crises and shifts in the political economy and must work to ensure that those most vulnerable are not only supported but also empowered to reshape the systems that affect their lives.

THE VALUE OF CRITICAL THEORY

The existence of both emancipatory forms of practice and an emergent body of research and theory on this practice raises questions about the epistemic basis of this rationality. What is it that we are seeking to emancipate people from and why? The emancipatory tradition in career guidance is pluralistic, but it does rely on a range of assumptions, basic tenets and some kind of shared worldview. The critical theory tradition is helpful in articulating and understanding what this is.

When we discuss critical theory, we are not simply talking about forms of theory which include critique, but rather of a longstanding, if contested, epistemic tradition. The term is variously used to describe German theoretical and philosophical traditions leading to, and proceeding from, the Frankfurt school exemplified in the work of Habermas (1984) and Adorno (1950) amongst others (Bohman, 2005; How, 2003). But other theories which variously draw on Marxism, structuralism and poststructuralism, feminism and postcolonialism and include the important work of theorists from outside of the Frankfurt school such as Foucault (1982) and Bourdieu (1977) who can also be described as advancing critical theory.

Additionally, other sociologists such as Weber (1968), Simmel (2011) and Durkheim (1898/1974) along with later theoretical work drawing on these theorists such as Moscovici (1988) can also be utilised for critical work. Both writers within the Frankfurt school and those outside it have addressed a range of questions related to careers, sometimes overtly using the terminology of careers, but for the most part these theorists are engaged with underpinning concepts and analyses around the nature of society, culture, politics, identity and power that can be repurposed and adapted to career studies rather than as direct authors of 'critical career theory' themselves.

Critical social research can be understood as a term encompassing an approach to social enquiry that attempts to go beneath surface appearance by critically engaging with prevailing conceptualisations of the social world (Harvey, 2022). Thomsen et al. (2022a) discuss the core features of critical theory, in the context of career studies, as follows.

CRITICAL THEORY:

Creates a radical imaginary

Critical theory poses a vision of an alternative or better society. It is defined by the normative belief that things can and should be better than they are and a belief that part of the work of theory is to bring about this change.

Attends to power

Critical theory recognises that social relations are not conducted on a level playing field. Different individuals, institutions and actors have different interests and different degrees of power. Social change emerges from the struggles between these different actors and theory should notice, describe and analyse these power imbalances and the struggles and dynamics between different forms of power.

Unmasks ideology

In modern and postmodern societies there are many things that obscure the operation of society and power. Critical theory is committed to analysing phenomena and systems and clarifying how they work and in whose interest. This is what Freire (1970/2005) described as 'conscientization' in his critical pedagogy.

Understands individuals to be in a dialectical relationship with context

While many disciplines focus primarily on individuals or on social systems, critical theory holds both of these in a dialectical relationship. The individual is both formed by and forms the social environment within which they live. This means that the individual and context are inseparable and that approaches to analysis which ignore this dialectical relationship are likely to miss important elements of processes that are social and psychological at the same time.

Views human beings as having a bounded but transformative agency

Critical theory recognises that human beings build their social world and that any social, political or economic formation can be contested and rebuilt. Because of this, human beings have agency that can transform their lives and the social world. However, this agency, as Marx (1852) famously noted, is not exercised 'under self-selected circumstances, but under circumstances existing already, given and transmitted from the past'. Therefore, agency is bounded by context and circumstance, with different individuals having different resources to shape their lives and the world around them. But critical theory also notes that when individuals come together into collectives, the potential for transformative agency increases.

Thomsen et al. (2022a) argue that:

When taken together, these five features define what we understand as critical theory. They provide both a framework for analysing career and career guidance and a rationale for undertaking this analysis.

Once again we can take inspiration from Marx and his 11th thesis on Feuerbach:

Philosophers have hitherto only interpreted the world in various ways; the point is to change it."

(Marx, 1845/2002)

The growth of emancipatory approaches in career guidance and the use of critical theory remains as an emergent movement in career studies. While an increasing number of practitioners and researchers are interested in these approaches the movement remains fragmented and lacking in both a deep theoretical underpinning and broad empirical support. These approaches remain stronger on critique, than on proposition and it remains difficult to describe what 'critical career theory' is to those outside of the field.

Yet, it is also important that concerns for theoretical clarity do not undermine the pluralism of critical approaches. This pluralism can be illustrated by three overlapping epistemic traditions, critical psychology, relational sociology, and postmodern discourse theories, which are discussed in more detail in Thomsen et al. (2022a). Together, they offer a multidimensional lens for interrogating the interaction of power, agency, and structure in career development.

We have already discussed how critical theory draws on a wide range of different traditions which variously emphasise concern about inequalities in class, gender, race and a variety of other characteristics or address particular themes such as the natural environment, socio-technological developments or the interdependence of global economic systems. While we would argue that these are bound together by the desire to create a radical imaginary, attend to power, unmask ideology, understand individuals as being in a dialectical relationship with their context, and viewing human beings as having a bounded but transformative agency, we would not seek to homogenise the diversity of critical career theory into a single, reductive position. Our difference is our strength, but our ability to engage with each other and act in solidarity where appropriate is also of central importance.

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Laclau and Mouffe (1985/2001) offer us two concepts that are useful in the organisation of such an academic movement. Firstly, the concept of 'chains of equivalence' which recognises multiple experiences and views the purpose of successful movements as the development of equivalent and linked claims to justice of different groups. So, the development of critical career theory is not about the establishment of ideological purity but rather about building a framework of mutual respect and action between a plurality of positions. Secondly, they offer us the idea of 'agonism' which celebrates the existence of pluralistic perspectives and asserts the right for adversaries to advocate for those perspectives. The practice of movement building and struggle is therefore one in which there is disagreement and debate within a 'shared adherence to the ethico-political principles of democracy' (Mouffe, 1999, p.755). This means that one of the jobs of a movement around critical career theory must be to encourage debate and celebrate disagreement as both an end and a means. The aim should be to foster a democratic and pluralistic intellectual community rather than viewing debate instrumentally as a tool for bringing about a unifying synthesis.

Within pluralism there should be mutual learning and development. The process of building chains of equivalence is a pedagogic one in which we should expect our positions and theories to change, develop and evolve, but not one of homogenisation in which everyone moves inevitably towards a single position. We have the right to ask others to listen to our perspectives, but not the right to demand compliance. The fact that we are engaged in a project of building critical career theory implies that we turn this criticality on ourselves and the others within our movement as well as on the oppressive hierarchies and power structures of the world around us.

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ENTER COCAG

The recognition of the need to organise critical perspectives within career theory, whilst also respecting differences and diversity has led us to conceptualise the network as the most relevant vehicle for driving forward thinking in critical career theory. This encouraged us to apply for funding from COST to establish the Critical perspectives on career and career guidance (COCAG) Action. A COST Action is an interdisciplinary research network that brings researchers, practitioners and other thought leaders together to investigate a topic of their choice for four years (COST, 2025).

The COCAG network seeks to gather scholars across Europe and beyond to explore how careers are changing in the contemporary world and consider what response is required from public policy and practice (COCAG, 2024). It is exploring the following research questions:

1. How can the challenges and changes that are happening to careers in the contemporary world be understood?
2. How can policymakers respond to contemporary challenges to individual's careers?
3. How can career guidance practice adopt a more critical stance to address the changing world more effectively?

COCAG will foster debate around these questions by stimulating publication projects, brokering relationships between researchers and developing new research directions. It will also support the public communication of research insights, findings and projects to policymakers and practitioners.

Capacity building is at the heart of the aims of COCAG. The Action will support the career development of early career researchers within the field by providing the opportunity to build international networks, co-publish with more experienced researchers, and participate in a wide variety of activities. The Action will also support collaboration between different countries including those countries in which the

field of career studies and the critical career theory perspective are less established. Finally, it will support practitioners' and policymakers' engagement with research and theory in the area and the mutual exchange and expansion of knowledge and expertise.

During its first six to twelve months, the Action has attracted over 400 members who have been working together through three working groups organised around the project's research questions. A key aim of this process has been sharing areas of interest and activity. Through a process of careful mapping and iterative discussion five main cross-cutting themes have emerged which describe the main areas of activity of the action. These can be summarised as follows.

MAIN AREAS OF ACTIVITY:

Careers in crisis

This theme addresses the contemporary career and asks how it is being changed and transformed by shifts in the political economy. We view the present time as being one of crisis and propose to explore how the labour market is responding to phenomena such as the interplay between globalisation and nationalism, the growth of precarity and inequality, rising unemployment and work-intensification and the green transition. These trends are fundamentally reshaping traditional career trajectories and challenging linear career development perspectives. Finally, this theme also explores the way that these phenomena shape and frame career guidance policy and practice.

Lifelong and lifewide learning in career

This theme addresses the process of career learning and the context of the education, training and skills systems. It views the education system as a key part of the political economy and recognises that wider crises will lead to changes in the education system. Additionally, it recognises that in the current period of crisis ensuring that equitable access to learning opportunities is maintained across different social and economic backgrounds is both less likely and more challenging. This theme also explores the relationships, interactions and transitions between formal and informal learning and between education and employment. Finally, it is interested in the context that the education system provides for people's career development and for career guidance.

MAIN AREAS OF ACTIVITY (CONTINUED):

Socio-technical careering

The Action has developed a particular interest in exploring the interaction between technology, society and career. Within the Action technology is viewed as a socially and historically created and situated construct rather than an actor in its own right. Key technologies which have been focused on include automation and artificial intelligence, the internet and digitalisation, as well as socio-technical phenomena such as the growth of digital surveillance, digital enclosure, the platformisation of the labour market and algorithmic decision-making. The theme explores how these developments are impacting on careers and on the policy and practice of career guidance.

Diversity and career

The Action recognises the dangers in creating totalising grand narratives about what is 'happening' in career and career guidance and correspondingly has a strong focus on the diversity of experiences. This theme explores the variety of ways in which people are different from one another (gender, race, geographical location and so on) and examines how these forms of diversity and difference have been used to make people vulnerable as well as how this diversity can be a source of strength and resource for people in their careers. Key concepts within this theme include culture and community and examine the complex ways in which these concepts interact with careers and career guidance.

Career imaginaries

Finally, the Action includes a theme which is imaginative in nature and looks forward to the building of a better world. This includes the examination of normative concepts which exist to improve people's careers and lives such as decent work, wellbeing, sustainability and social justice as well as more utopian imaginaries of what careering might be like in new and different forms of society. A key question within this theme is how people's careers and the policy and practice of career guidance can contribute to forms of social transformation.

These five themes are explored through the frame of the research questions and working groups. **Working Group One** is interested in examining how we understand the context in relation to each of these themes, what is driving the phenomena within the themes, in whose interest do they work, how can we better theorise such phenomena and what is the possibility for changes? **Working Group Two** will primarily look at how policymakers are responding to these issues, why they are they doing this, how this intersects with career guidance, what other possibilities exist for policy and how researchers,

practitioners and the populace might exert influence on policy? **Working Group Three** will explore how these issues impact on and can be addressed by career guidance practice, where the difficulties and challenges lie, and what approaches offer more possibilities?

The themes summarise the content and main areas of inquiry within the COCAG Action, while the working groups provide the scale and focus points from which these issues are being addressed. This leaves an outstanding area for further work which deals with the epistemic

basis and diversity of the Action. So far, we have argued for the use of critical theory as the epistemic foundation of the Action. As discussed above, critical theory is a pluralistic tradition that encompasses a wide range of perspectives. We have used Thomsen et al.'s (2022a) summary of critical theory to provide an epistemic starting point for the Action. This argues that participants in the Action should be united in their desire to create a radical imaginary, attend to power, unmask ideology, understand individuals to be in a dialectical relationship with context and view human beings as having a bounded but transformative agency. Yet, as has been subsequently argued, there are many ways to do this that draw on different epistemic traditions.

In Thomsen et al.'s (2022a) special issue of the *British Journal of Guidance and Counselling* they identify critical psychology, relational sociology and postmodern discourse theory as three key epistemic bases for critical career studies. But, the COCAG Action has drawn on a much wider range of disciplines, national contexts and epistemic backgrounds. These diverse theoretical perspectives intersect with the themes and research questions of the Action to produce new forms of critical career theory. Most authors of this position paper are based in Europe which has a pluralistic tradition in career studies with scholars from education, psychology, sociology, social psychology, management and organisation studies. Scholars also have a strong history of connecting to policy and practice in their work. (Weber et al., 2018). This is a distinctive element of our network. Such plurality is a strength to build upon albeit this means dealing with challenging disciplinary assumptions, norms and practices in relation to activities such as publishing and knowledge creation. Given this, there remains outstanding work for the Action to map these epistemic positions and gain a better understanding of the theoretical tributaries that are coming together in critical career theory.

Ultimately the aim is to use COCAG to move the field forwards in several ways. In relation to *theory*, we hope to strengthen the critique of existing career theory, to make the shift from critique to proposition and establish a more clearly demarcated body of critical career theory. This theoretical work can unfold alongside and in interaction with new *research* which is informed by critical perspectives and creates a growing evidence base for the utility of critical perspectives in both research and career guidance practice.

Beyond the scientific domain we hope that the project will have an influence on policy which may include both finding a basis on which to engage with existing policymakers from all political traditions around critical perspectives and specifically engaging political traditions that are aligned with the critical perspective. This may mean working with the parties of the green and new left, trade unions and extra-parliamentary social movements to develop their understanding of career. It is also likely to mean building stronger frameworks for practice that are informed by critical career theory and working to stimulate the development and reflection on a range of new critical career guidance practices. Such work is also likely to require COCAG to engage with the existing institutions of career guidance (professional and employer bodies, learned societies and NGOs) to move critical perspectives from the periphery to a more central place in the institutions and ideologies of career studies and career guidance.

Advocacy is also central to this endeavour. As we develop theoretical and empirical insights, we must also strengthen the field's capacity to act – to influence public policy, challenge unjust systems, and stand alongside individuals and communities navigating structural disadvantage. Critical career theory does not remain in the realm of critique; it demands engagement, solidarity, and advocacy as strategies of hope and change.

FINAL THOUGHTS

This position paper provides a detailed conceptual underpinning for the work of the COCAG network. We hope that it also provides a rallying cry and organising impetus for critical career theory more widely. At its centre is the claim that we are living in a world in crisis. The crisis is unfolding in a way that is increasing inequality and driving down people's likelihood of establishing a decent and meaningful life and career. The existing body of career theory is unable to provide a way forward in such times. Our contention is that drawing on the tradition of critical theory provides us with a powerful way forwards.

Critical theory remains as an emergent tradition within the interdisciplinary field of career studies. It provides us with tools and insights that help us to both better understand the world in which we are careering and to develop new strategies that allow us cope with, resist and ultimately transform the world around us. Critical career theory is born of a profound optimism of the will, that it is possible to build a world in which everyone can create a meaningful, socially useful, sustainable and sustaining career. It is hoped that this paper and the COCAG Action can make a contribution towards this aim.

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